

Recurrent Gynecomastia In a Teenage Male – Bilateral Pseudoangiomatous Stromal Hyperplasia (Pash)

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ABSTRACT

A 19-year-old male underwent cosmetic surgery for bilateral gynecomastia of idiopathic origin. 9 months postoperatively patient presented with recurrence. Patient underwent diagnostic workup for endocrine causes, testicular exam, breast imaging, and biopsy consistent with fatty tissue. The patient underwent a second gynecomastectomy and pathology was consistent with features of PASH.

BACKGROUND

Pseudoangiomatous stromal hyperplasia (PASH) is a relatively uncommon benign proliferative lesion of the supportive breast tissue made up of connective tissue and blood vessels. PASH was first described in 1986 by Vuitch, Erlandon, and Rosen and was initially thought to be a variant form of mamillary hamartomas [1]. Most cases of PASH are slow growing unilateral lumps, making a bilateral rapid growing lesion extremely rare [2].

PASH presents almost exclusively in females, typically perimenopausal and premenopausal females with an average age of around 40 years old. Although rare, PASH can also be seen in adolescents, postmenopausal females, males, and those on hormone replacement therapy. PASH is thought to make up anywhere from 20-47% of all gynecomastia cases. Gynecomastia is a benign enlargement of glandular mammary tissue in males due to an imbalance of estrogen to androgen levels [3]. While PASH is almost exclusively seen in the breast there have been several cases reported in the axillary, perianal area, perineum, and labia majora [4-5].

The etiology of PASH is unknown but thought to be influenced by hormonal factors specifically progesterone. It is linked to the initial phases of breast maturation as well as with hormonal changes during menstruation. Due to this, it is thought that a history of oral contraceptives or hormone replacement therapy are possible risk factors [6]. With the limited research on PASH to date, most cases are idiopathic.

CASE REPORT

The patient is a 19-year-old male that initially developed breast tissue at approximately 12 years of age. Breast development was slowly progressive and persistent. Breast size had stabilized over the previous 2 years as had his weight. Physical exam was consistent with the presence of breast tissue. He had no history of contributing medications. Testicular exam was normal. Endocrine exam was not indicated due to stabilization. Breast imaging was required per his insurance and was normal. His insurance denied coverage and he elected for cosmetic resection (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Initial breast presentation prior to first cosmetic resection

The patient underwent gynecomastectomy, without incident and recovered well. Approximately 200g of fibrofatty breast tissue was removed from each side and the patient recovered without complication. 3 months after surgery the patient returned for post operative photos (**Figure 2**). Photos revealed overall improvement in contour and no significant post-operative concerns.

Figure 2: 3month post-operative of initial cosmetic resection with overall improvement in contour and no significant post-operative concerns

The patient returned 6 months later with concerns for recurrence especially on the right side (**Figure 3**). No hematoma or seroma was identified. A smooth round rubbery mass was noted on the right side. The texture was most consistent with a lipoma but given his post-operative state, additional workup was indicated. Endocrine evaluation was non-contributory. Repeat mammogram and ultrasound demonstrated no evidence of malignancy but marked bilateral gynecomastia. Evaluation with a breast oncologist resulted in a biopsy consistent with fatty breast tissue and no evidence of malignancy.

Figure 3: 6 months post operatively from initial cosmetic resection with concerns for recurrence greater on the right side

The patient was rescheduled for mastectomy and this was performed 10 months after the original resection. 70 grams of fibroadipose tissue was removed from the right side and 57 grams from the left side. Final pathology demonstrated bilateral gynecomastia with pseudoangiomatous stromal hyperplasia (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Pathology from bilateral tissue samples demonstrating pseudoangiomatous stromal hyperplasia

The patient was followed clinically for 4 months after surgery without evidence of recurrence (**Figure 5**). The patient continues to follow with the breast oncologist with no additional signs of recurrence over one 3 year out from surgery.

Figure 5: 4 months post-operatively from second gynecomastectomy with no significant concerns or signs of recurrence

DISCUSSION

Pathologically, PASH is grossly a gray/white or tan lesion that is smooth, circumscribed, and rubbery. It is typically not hemorrhagic or necrotic [7]. When it presents as a palpable mass it is classified as nodular or tumorous [8]. PASH on histology is described as pseudoangiomatous hyperplasia of intralobular breast stromal myofibroblasts [4]. It appears as anastomosing channels lined with spindle cells in a collagenous matrix [9]. The spindle cells have bland nuclei and lack atypia. They have progesterone and estrogen receptors and stains positive for vimentin, actin, desmin, BCL-2, and CD34. They are negative for endothelial markers, S100, and cytokeratin [10]. The angular slit-like spaces lacking red blood cells, formed by fixation artifact, and inter-anastomosis differentiate PASH from similar conditions including low grade angiosarcoma, fibroadenoma, and phyllodes tumors that make up part of the differential diagnosis. PASH is most commonly misdiagnosed as fibroadenoma [11]. Angiosarcoma can be ruled out by lack of cellular atypia, infiltration, and immunohistochemistry being negative for von Willebrand factor [12]. Phyllodes presents as much more cellular than PASH on histology. Misdiagnosis can potentially lead to unnecessary treatment or poor outcomes.

PASH is usually an incidental discovery in routine breast biopsies for females. In males it is a much rarer finding but it is typically brought to medical attention as gynecomastia. When it presents as a mass lesion in males or females it is typically a painless, palpable, mobile, unilateral mass [13]. This case is unique, in part, due to its bilateral presentation. Patients' chief complaint is often concern for breast asymmetry causing emotional or psychological distress. In a subset of cases PASH can present with back pain, breast tenderness, or non-bloody nipple discharge but is largely asymptomatic in most cases. PASH can be diagnosed by mammogram, ultrasound, or biopsy. Diagnosis of PASH on mammography shows a circular mass with no microcalcifications [10]. On ultrasound, PASH presents variably but often as a homogenous hypoechoic solid mass without posterior shadowing [14]. MRI is not a typical diagnostic tool for PASH [4] but does show focal enhancement on imaging [15]. Regardless of various diagnostic imaging tools, diagnosis can only be confirmed by biopsy or excision and pathological examination [16].

PASH is most commonly treated by surgical excision and is curative without recurrence. Approximately 7-22% of cases do recur which require mastectomy to be curative [17]. Our case report is a unique finding of rapidly occurring

bilateral recurrence. There is current research about tamoxifen, an estrogen receptor modulator, as a possible medication therapy^[18]. Rapidly growing cases of PASH are rare so another treatment approach has been monitoring for changes in patients that do not wish to have surgery. Current research shows that PASH has little to no association with progressing to or increasing the risk of malignancy. At this time, it does show a rare association with ductal carcinoma insitu.

A diffuse, bilateral, and recurring breast enlargement associated with PASH in a young male, as described in this case, is extremely rare, and very few similar cases have been reported in the literature.

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